

NUMERICAL STUDY OF PHASE-CHANGE PHENOMENA: A CONSERVATIVE LINEARIZED ENTHALPY APPROACH

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ABSTRACT

Solid-liquid phase-change phenomena play a key role in the thermal hydraulics of Molten Salt Reactors (MSR's). Amongst key areas of interest are the design of the freeze plug and the analysis of accident scenarios where solidification of the fuel salt might pose a risk. As such, accurate numerical models coupling the solid-liquid phase transition with fluid flow and thermal effects are highly desired for a safe and efficient design of the MSR's. Nowadays, the most widely used models for modelling macroscopic phase change are the apparent heat capacity method and the source-based enthalpy approach. However, these models suffer from low accuracy in the limit of large time-steps and a small mushy zone and slow convergence respectively. In addition, smearing the latent heat-peak through the introduction of the so-called 'mushy-zone' does not reflect the physics of isothermal phase-change and may introduce an additional source of error. For this reason, we model melting/solidification phase-change through the so-called linearized enthalpy approach, where the energy equation is linearized around a previously known value of the volumetric enthalpy. This approach is inherently energy-conservative, without the need for a mushy zone. Both the classical Stefan problem and gallium melting in a rectangular enclosure with heated side walls are considered as numerical benchmarking cases. For the latter, the linearized enthalpy method is validated using both available experimental data and a previous numerical campaign with the source-based enthalpy approach, and the accuracy of both approaches is compared. As such, this study contributes to the continuous advancement of melting and solidification modelling capabilities.

KEYWORDS

Solid-Liquid Phase Change, Linearized-Enthalpy Method, Finite-Volume

1. INTRODUCTION

Melting/solidification phase-change has been an extensive field of research for the past few decades, due to the complexity of the physics and mathematics involved and its relevance for many processes and applications, such as latent heat storage [1] and metallurgy [2]. In the present case, the role of melting and solidification phenomena in the Molten Salt Fast Reactor (MSFR), one of the six Generation IV nuclear reactors which is currently being developed in the framework of the European SAMOSAFER project (2019-2023), is of particular interest.

The reference MSFR is a fast spectrum, 3000 MW_{th} breeder reactor, with an average operating temperature of 725 °C and a maximum fuel salt temperature of 750 °C [3]. The MSFR operates in the thorium fuel cycle, using a mixture of lithium, thorium and uranium fluorides as both the liquid fuel and the coolant. Compared to conventional light water reactors (LWR's), the MSFR produces both less and shorter-lived radioactive waste, due to the fast spectrum, a higher fuel burnup and the continuous removal of fission products through helium bubbling or pyrochemical processes [3]. In addition, the MSFR is self-regulating due to a strong negative temperature coefficient and may be operated at ambient pressure [3]. Finally, the safety of the MSFR is further enhanced through the so-called freeze plug, which is designed to melt in case of a severe accident scenario, draining the fuel into sub-critical storage tanks [3].

Melting and solidification phase change phenomena play an important role in the design and operation of the MSFR, in particular for the prediction of the melting time of the freeze-plug [3], the analysis of safety scenarios where solidification of salt might pose a risk (i.e. freeze-up in pipes and the steam generator, leading to clogging and potentially to rupture) [4] and the prediction of the possible formation of a thin film of solid salt at the core vessel wall, protecting the wall from corrosion [5]. For this reason, a good understanding of the physics involved as well as the further improvement of the current melting and solidification modelling capabilities are highly desirable.

Despite extensive research and continued development, numerical modelling of melting and solidification problems is still challenging. A large part of the complexity arises from the displacement of the solid-liquid interface (i.e. moving boundary problem) and the corresponding discontinuities in the enthalpy (strong discontinuity) and temperature fields (weak discontinuity) [6]. To further complicate matters, most melting/solidification problems of practical relevance are intertwined with fluid flow, solid settling [7] or neutronics [5]. Though multiple classifications of melting and solidification models exist in literature, we chose to separate them into explicit and implicit methods according to the procedure used to locate the moving boundary. In the explicit methods, the position of the melting/solidification interface at the new time-step is directly determined through application of the Stefan condition on the interface at the previous time-step. On the other hand, in the implicit methods, the position of the melting/solidification interface is inferred from the enthalpy or temperature field.

The most well-known explicit methods are the transformed grid approach [8] [9], the level-set method [10] and the phase-field method [11]. The transformed grid approach fixes the solid-liquid interface in time and space through the application of a suitable coordinate transformation (e.g. Landau [8] [9]). The main advantage of this approach is that the governing heat and fluid flow equations are solved on a fixed rectangular and uniformly spaced grid with no loss of discretization accuracy in the vicinity of the solid-liquid interface position [8]. However, for complex problems involving a complex geometry or a complex evolution of the (multiple) solid-liquid interface(s), the co-ordinate transformation yields poor results and one has to resort to grid-generation instead, which is a computationally expensive process [8] [9]. In addition, the appropriate form of the coordinate transformation or grid generator are problem specific, and therefore generalization of this approach is difficult [8] [12]. Regarding the level-set and phase-field methods, these have been mainly applied to microscale phase-change phenomena, such as dendritic solidification, and were thus not considered for the present work. For this reason, we focus on implicit methods. The advantage of these models is that they are easy to implement, do not require remeshing and can deal relatively easily with complex multi-dimensional problems and multiple interfaces [6]. However, compared to a grid-conforming approach with an explicit tracking of the solid-liquid interface, implicit fixed grid methods are less accurate and a very fine mesh may be needed to obtain grid-independent results [8] [9].

The two most common implicit fixed grid methods for simulation melting and solidification problems are the apparent heat capacity method [13] and the source-based enthalpy approach [14]. The former replaces the heat capacity with an approximation of the true enthalpy-temperature derivative (i.e. apparent heat capacity), whereas the latter splits the total enthalpy into a sensible and a latent contribution, which is treated as a source term in the energy equation. In both methods, the latent heat peak at $T = T_m$ is smeared out over a small artificial temperature region (i.e. mushy zone), typically using a linear approximation of the Dirac delta function. The main drawback of the apparent heat capacity method is its poor energy conservation: for a combination of a too large time-step and a too small mushy zone, the latent heat peak may be skipped, leading to a deteriorated solution quality [6]. Several methods have been proposed to remedy this problem, including spatial or temporal averaging of the apparent heat capacity or a temperature correction after each time-step [6]. On the other hand, because the value of the latent heat contribution at the current time-step is not known a priori, the source-based enthalpy approach requires an iterative solution update and may be slow to converge [14].

Recent efforts towards improving and extending the melting-solidification implicit fixed grid modelling capabilities have been directed towards coupling a melting/solidification model to a RANS [15] or a LES [16] turbulence model, coupling a melting/solidification model to neutronics [5], coupling the macroscopic enthalpy method to a microscopic phase field mode [17], including a solid-settling term in the momentum equation [7] and improving the spatial accuracy of the numerical method through a suitable adaptive meshing strategy [18] or by coupling the melting/solidification model to a discontinuous Galerkin framework [19]. In addition, attempts have been made to develop an implicit fixed-grid method that combines the best features from the apparent heat capacity method and the source-based enthalpy approach, i.e. fast convergence and good accuracy/reliability. Here, the linearized enthalpy approach, also referred to as the 'optimum' approach, has shown to be very promising [20] [21] [1]. The idea is to perform a first order Taylor linearization of the enthalpy around a previously known value of the temperature and subsequently converge the energy equation through a series of Newton iterations. The 'linearized enthalpy approach' has been shown to achieve faster convergence at each time-step as compared to the source-based enthalpy approach [20] [1].

In this spirit, and drawing inspiration from the works of *Nedjar et al* and *Faden et al* in particular [21] [1], we present our 'linearized enthalpy method'. The main attractive features of our approach are a fully conservative energy-equation, the elimination of the need for a mushy zone, and a robust way of dealing with the variation of thermo-physical properties across the solid-liquid interface. Hereby, we aim to contribute to the continuous advancement of melting and solidification modelling capabilities. Our model is validated using the 1D Stefan problem and gallium melting in a rectangular cavity with heated side wall [22] as respectively an analytical and experimental reference solution. For the latter, we compare the results of our present numerical investigation with previous numerical campaigns and draw a preliminary conclusion regarding the performance of our model with respect to the source-based enthalpy approach.

2. NUMERICAL METHOD

2.1. Linearized Enthalpy Approach: Model Equations

The starting point for the linearized enthalpy approach is the volumetric enthalpy transport equation in conservative form*:

$$\frac{DH}{Dt} = \frac{\partial H}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial (v_i H)}{\partial x_i} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left(\lambda \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_i} \right) \quad (1)$$

By treating the liquid and solid-regions as a single domain (which is the foundation of implicit fixed grid approaches), a non-linearity is introduced in the enthalpy-temperature coupling:

$$T(H) = \begin{cases} \frac{H}{\rho_s c_{p,s}}, & H \leq \rho_s c_{p,s} T_m \\ T_m, & \rho_s c_{p,s} T_m < H < \rho_s c_{p,s} T_m + \rho_s L \\ T_m + \frac{H - (\rho_s c_{p,s} T_m + \rho_s L)}{\rho_l c_{p,l}}, & H \geq \rho_s c_{p,s} T_m + \rho_s L \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

For this reason, a separate melting/solidification procedure must be adopted. Building on the work of *Swaminathan et al*, *Nedjar et al* and *Faden et al* [20] [21] [1], we perform a 1st order Taylor linearization of the volumetric enthalpy around a previously known value of the temperature:

$$H = H^* + \left. \frac{dH}{dT} \right|^* (T - T^*) \quad (3)$$

Here, the asterix refers to the estimation of the temperature and enthalpy fields at the previous iteration. Since the enthalpy-temperature derivative is undefined at $T = T_m$, the true derivative is replaced with a suitable approximation. Whilst the approximation chosen does not influence the results, it may affect the convergence rate and the robustness of the simulation [21]. Performing a second order implicit BDF2 time-integration, the full energy equation may be written as:

$$\begin{aligned} \left. \frac{dH}{dT} \right|^{n+1,*} \left(\frac{3T^{n+1}}{2\Delta t} + \frac{\partial (v_i T^{n+1})}{\partial x_i} \right) - \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left(\lambda \frac{\partial T^{n+1}}{\partial x_i} \right) = \\ \left. \frac{dH}{dT} \right|^{n+1,*} \left(\frac{3T^{n+1,*}}{2\Delta t} + \frac{\partial (v_i T^{n+1,*})}{\partial x_i} \right) - \frac{3H^{n+1,*} - 4H^n + H^{n-1}}{2\Delta t} + \frac{\partial (v_i H^{n+1,*})}{\partial x_i} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Regarding the enforcement of the no-slip condition at the solid-liquid interface position, we consider the Darcy source term approach [14]. This approach is most commonly used and has been shown to have

*Source terms are not included here.

better performance compared to the other two approaches (i.e. the switch-off and variable viscosity techniques) [6]. Assuming incompressible flow with a Newtonian fluid and using the *Boussinesq* approximation for the natural convection effects, the momentum equation may be written as:

$$\rho_l \frac{Dv_i}{Dt} = \rho_l \frac{\partial v_i}{\partial t} + \rho_l \frac{\partial (v_j v_i)}{\partial x_j} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left[\mu \left(\frac{\partial v_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial v_j}{\partial x_i} \right) \right] - \frac{\partial p}{\partial x_i} + \rho_l g_i \beta (T - T_m) - C \frac{(1 - \alpha)^2}{\alpha^3 + b} v_i \quad (5)$$

Here, the last term in the equation is referred to as the Darcy source term, which is based on the Carman-Kozeny equations for flow in porous media [14]. In this case, we calculate the liquid fraction based on the volumetric enthalpy:

$$\alpha(H) = \begin{cases} 0, & H \leq \rho_s c_{p,s} T_m \\ \frac{H - \rho_s c_{p,s} T_m}{\rho_s L}, & \rho_s c_{p,s} T_m < H < \rho_s c_{p,s} T_m + \rho_s L \\ 1, & H \geq \rho_s c_{p,s} T_m + \rho_s L \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

At each time-step, we first solve the momentum equation and subsequently solve the energy equation through a series of Newton iterations, according to the following steps:

1. Solve the momentum equation (equation 5).
2. Solve the linearized volumetric enthalpy transport equation.
3. Update the enthalpy (see equation 3)[†].
4. Force the temperature back on the enthalpy-temperature curve.
5. Check the convergence. If the convergence criterium for the energy equation has been fulfilled, proceed to the next timestep, else overwrite the old iteration values with the new values and return to step 2.

The convergence criterium at each timestep is defined as:

$$\max\left(\sqrt{res \cdot res} \frac{\Delta t}{E_{tot}}, \max\left(\left| \frac{T - T^*}{T} \right| \right)\right) < tol \quad (7)$$

Here, E_{tot} is the total energy in the system and res is the residual of the volumetric enthalpy transport equation, which may be defined as:

$$res = \frac{3H^{n+1,*} - 4H^n + H^{n-1}}{2\Delta t} + \frac{\partial (v_i H^{n+1,*})}{\partial x_i} - \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left(\lambda \frac{\partial T^{n+1}}{\partial x_i} \right) \quad (8)$$

[†]The true enthalpy-temperature derivative may be replaced by an approximation hereof. This may help with the convergence [21]

2.2. Computational Settings

The linearized enthalpy approach was implemented in a 1D in-house fortran code [23] and in OpenFOAM 7.0 for validation against the 1D Stefan problem and gallium melting in a rectangular cavity with heated side wall [22] respectively [‡]. Spatial discretization is performed with the central differencing scheme for the diffusion term (second order accuracy), the linear upwind scheme for the convection in the momentum equation (second order accuracy) and the QUICK scheme for the convection terms in the energy equation (third order accuracy). Implicit time-integration was performed with the second order BDF2 scheme. The velocity-pressure coupling was solved with OpenFOAM's PIMPLE algorithm (i.e. a transient form of the SIMPLE algorithm). In the 1D in-house code, the system of equations is solved using LAPACK's solver for banded matrices, dgbsv. In OpenFOAM, OpenFOAM's 'smooth solver' was used for the velocity (based on the symmetric Gauss Seidel method), and the equations for the other field variables (pressure, temperature) were solved through the geometric algebraic multigrid method. Adaptive time-stepping was used, based on a maximum *Courant* number of 1. Finally, we use a Darcy coefficient equal to $C = 10^{11}$ and the reference temperature in the *Boussinesq* approximation is set to the melting temperature. The parameter b is included in the Darcy source term for numerical purposes to prevent division by zero and is set equal to $b = 10^{-11}$.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. One Dimensional Solidification

One-dimensional solidification, also known as the Stefan problem, is often selected as a numerical benchmark case for phase change problems. After all, one of the best ways to evaluate the performance of a numerical method is by comparing their performance with an available analytic solution. We consider a one-dimensional bar of length $l = 0.05m$, where one side is suddenly lowered to below the melting temperature: $T(0, t) = 268K < T_m$ and the other side is described by a homogeneous Neumann boundary condition ($\left. \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} \right|_{t,L} = 0$). The phase change material matches the thermophysical properties of water (see table I). For the one-dimensional solidification case, we chose the following approximation of the enthalpy-temperature derivative:

$$\frac{dH}{dT} \approx \frac{1}{2} (\rho_s c_{p,s} + \rho_l c_{p,l}) \quad (9)$$

Due to the absence of convection, the problem may be described by one pair of heat conduction equations, one for each phase (solid and liquid phase).

[‡]Due to difficulties when parallizing the code, we chose to implement the convection term in the following form: $\frac{\partial(v_i H^{n+1})}{\partial x_i} = \rho_l c_{p,l} \frac{\partial(v_i T^{n+1,*})}{\partial x_i} + \rho_s L \frac{\partial(v_i \alpha^{n+1,*})}{\partial x_i} + \frac{dH}{dT} \Big|^{n+1,*} \frac{\partial(v_i T^{n+1})}{\partial x_i} - \frac{dH}{dT} \Big|^{n+1,*} \frac{\partial(v_i T^n)}{\partial x_i}$. In principle, this should lead to the same results.

	Solid	Liquid
Density [kg m⁻³]	917	1000
Specific heat capacity [J kg⁻¹]	4200	2100
Thermal conductivity [W m⁻¹ K⁻¹]	2.16	0.575
Latent heat [J kg⁻¹]	333000	
Melting Temperature [K]	273	

Table I. Thermophysical properties used in one-dimensional Stefan numerical benchmark problem.

Figure 1 shows the numerical prediction versus the analytical solution for a one-phase Stefan problem (i.e. the same thermophysical properties for the liquid and solid phase, in this case the thermophysical properties of the liquid where used). Here, 256 control volumes where used with a time-step of 0.1 s (BDF2 time-integration). Each timestep, around 11 iterations where needed to reach the convergence criterion of $\max(\sqrt{res \cdot res} \frac{\Delta t}{E_{tot}}, \max(|\frac{T-T^*}{T}|)) < 10^{-9}$. The numerical solid-liquid interface position was found based on $\alpha(H) = 0.5$ §. For both the temperature field and the solid-liquid interface position, the agreement with the analytical results is very good and it is nearly impossible to distinguish the numerical and analytical solutions by eye.

Figure 1. Numerical prediction of the temperature with linearized enthalpy model [24] versus analytical solution for a one-phase Stefan problem, with 256 control volumes, and a time-step of 0.1 s with BDF 2 time-integration after 500 s, for the temperature field and interface position respectively.

Figure 2 depicts the norm of the error in the temperature field after 100 s of simulation time

$$\left(\frac{\int_0^L (T_{num} - T_{an})^2 dx}{\int_0^L T_{an}^2 dx} \right),$$

for both the single and the two-phase Stefan problems. Both the single and the two-phase Stefan problems display an convergence rate of approximately $O(h)$, whereas the optimal convergence rate for a central differencing scheme would be $O(h^2)$. The sub optimal convergence rate arises from the poor approximation of the interface discontinuities by a continuous polynomial function (in this case linear), and is consistent with the theoretical convergence rate estimate for modelling the two-phase Stefan problem with the enthalpy method by *Jerome et al* [25].

§Please note that although the 'linearized enthalpy approach' does not require the use of a mushy zone, in practice the interface is still smeared out over one mesh cell due to the continuous nature of the finite volume approximation within a cell.

Figure 2. L2 norm of the relative difference between the numerical [24] and analytical temperature fields, for both a single phase and two-phase Stefan problem. The total time was 100 s and the time step was 0.01 s.

3.2. Gallium melting in a rectangular closure

The second test case is gallium melting in a rectangular enclosure, which is frequently used for the assessment of numerical solid-liquid phase change modelling approaches, due to the availability of well-documented experimental results [2] [26] [27]. The classic experiment features a rectangular test cell with inner dimensions of 88.9 mm in width, 63.5 mm in height and 38.1 mm in depth. The left hot wall is kept at 311.15 K and the right cold wall is kept at the initial condition, i.e. 301.45 K [2]. The rest of the walls were adiabatic. For the gallium case, the enthalpy-temperature derivative was approximated as follows:

$$\frac{dH}{dT} \approx \begin{cases} \rho_s c_{p,s}, & H \leq \rho_s c_{p,s} T_m \\ 100 \rho_s c_{p,s}, & \rho_s c_{p,s} T_m < H < \rho_s c_{p,s} T_m + \rho_s L \\ \rho_l c_{p,l}, & H \geq \rho_s c_{p,s} T_m + \rho_s L \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

The thermophysical properties of gallium are given in table II.

	Solid	Liquid
Dynamic Viscosity [N s m⁻²]	1.81 · 10 ⁻³	
Thermal expansion coefficient [K⁻¹]	1.2 · 10 ⁻⁴	
Density [kg m⁻³]	6093	6093
Specific heat capacity [J kg⁻¹]	381.5	381.5
Thermal conductivity [W m⁻¹ K⁻¹]	32.0	32.0
Latent heat [J kg⁻¹]	80200	
Melting Temperature [K]	302.93	

Table II. Thermophysical properties of gallium [28] [29] [30].

Whilst multiple 2D computations have been performed of gallium melting in a rectangular enclosure [14] [28] [30], 3D computations are rare. However, recently it has been shown that the multicellular flow pattern observed in the 2D computations does not exist in the 3D numerical simulations, due to the presence of the walls in the third direction which suppress the flow [29]. In addition, the 3D simulation includes the presence of a secondary flow in the depth direction, which is absent in the 2D case [29]. As such, the use of a 2D domain does not accurately reflect the physics of the problem, and the present numerical work uses a 3D computational domain for validating the numerical method. To reduce computational effort, the domain is sliced in half along the width axis, where a symmetry boundary condition is specified at the central plane.

Figure 3a depicts the solid-liquid interface position for different mesh resolutions (The amount of control volumes in the depth direction was equal to 20 for all meshes). We compare the predictions of the linearized enthalpy method for the solid-liquid interface position with those of *Gau et Viskanta et al* [2]. Consistent with the work of *Hannoun et al* [28], even the results from the $200 \cdot 200 \cdot 20$ mesh are not mesh independent: to achieve mesh independent results, a prohibitively fine mesh is needed. In order to keep the computational effort affordable, the $200 \cdot 200 \cdot 20$ mesh was used for the subsequent analysis. With this mesh, around 7 iterations were needed at each time-step to reach the convergence criterion of $\max(\sqrt{res \cdot res} \frac{\Delta t}{E_{tot}}, \max(|\frac{T-T^*}{T}|)) < 10^{-5}$. A very good agreement was observed between the present numerical campaign and the previous numerical and experimental campaigns [29] [2] for the solid-liquid interphase position at different times. Despite the significantly finer mesh of *Wittig et al* of $280 \cdot 120 \cdot 200$ control volumes, the present numerical campaign with the $200 \cdot 200 \cdot 20$ mesh shows slightly better agreement with the experimental results for the solid-liquid interface position, however this may also be due to (minor) differences in mesh resolution and the thermophysical properties used in the simulation.

Figure 3. Mesh convergence study, evaluated at $t = 1140$ s, and comparison of current numerical campaign [24] with experimental results [2] and previous numerical campaign [29] respectively for the solid-liquid interface position, plotted on the xy plane. The solid-liquid interface position was obtained by sampling the isosurface $\alpha(H) = 1$ (see equation 6) using the postprocessing tool ParaView.

Mesh	Error (%)
50 · 50 · 20	11.35
100 · 100 · 20	10.53
200 · 200 · 20	9.38
280 · 120 · 200 [29]	10.25

Table III. The percentile error in the solid-liquid interface position. The percentile error was calculated as the mean value of $100 \frac{|s_{exp} - s_{num}|}{s_{exp}}$

Figure 4 shows the evolution of the buoyancy driven flow-field, for $t = 120$ s, 360s, 750s and 1140s. At $t = 120$ s, the influence of the buoyancy-driven flow on the solid-liquid front is still relatively small: the shape of the interface is almost flat. Over time, the influence of the natural convection circulation on the solid-liquid front becomes more pronounced and the front assumes a bugle shape. Contrary to previous 2D numerical campaigns [14] [28] [30], and in line with the 3D numerical campaign of *Wittig et al*, no multivortex structure was observed. Likewise, the aforementioned multivortex natural circulation can clearly be observed for the 2D simulation case (see figure 5). When plotting the velocity on the xz plane for the 3D case, a non-zero velocity component in the depth (z) direction may be observed (see figure 6). This indicates the presence of a secondary flow, apart from the main natural circulation loop. Both the absence of the multi cellular natural convection, as well as the presence of secondary flow, highlight the importance of performing numerical benchmark studies of melting with natural convection with the full 3D experimental geometry.

Figure 4. Evolution of natural convection flow field for the 3D 200 · 200 · 20 mesh at respectively 120, 360, 750 and 1140 s [24], plotted on the xy plane.

Figure 5. Evolution of natural convection flow field for the 2D 200 · 200 mesh at respectively 120 and 360 s [24], plotted on the xy plane.

Figure 6. Flow-field for the 3D 200 · 200 · 20 mesh plotted on the xz plane, for $t = 1140$ s [24].

4. CONCLUSIONS

This work introduced a new variant of the linearized enthalpy approach, where the volumetric enthalpy is linearized around the latest values of the temperature. The linearized enthalpy method was subsequently validated using one-dimensional solidification and gallium melting in a rectangular enclosure as benchmark cases. A good agreement was obtained between the results of the present numerical campaign and both the analytical solution for the one-dimensional solidification case and the experimental results for the gallium melting in a rectangular enclosure case. Compared to the previous numerical campaign of Wittig *et al* [29], where the source-based enthalpy approach was used, a slightly better agreement with the experimental results was obtained in the present work with the linearized enthalpy approach. However, no hard conclusions can be drawn regarding the accuracy of the two approaches, due to (minor) differences in mesh resolution and the thermophysical properties used in the simulation. The present numerical campaign further demonstrated the importance of performing phase change simulations in 3D, due to the damping effect of the walls in the width direction and the presence of secondary flow, influencing the flow-field and hereby also the displacement of the solid-liquid interface position.

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